

**STUDY ON THE DEGRADATION PHENOMENA OF SMC IN ALKALI CONDITION
BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD**

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ABSTRACT

The corrosion phenomena of SMC used for the structures in the water and chemical environments was investigated in an 0.5-N alkaline solution. The dynamic degradation of mechanical properties caused by corrosion was quantitatively evaluated in terms of the fracture toughness values. Microscopic cracks on the surface of test specimen and the change of cracks region were measured and the change of fracture phenomena were determined by the acoustic emission (AE) method. The results indicate that the fracture toughness values of the test specimen surely decrease with the increase of the immersion time of it sunk in the alkaline solution because the fiber is debonded from the resin.

Keywords: SMC, Corrosion, AE method, Fracture Toughness and Fracture mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

FRP has recently been used in increasingly severer environments. It is recognized that the strength of the glass fiber is more deteriorated by corrosion in alkaline environment than in acid one. The variation of the corrosion of the notched FRP test specimen with time and the deterioration process of strength were examined. Although many papers on the corrosion resistance of FRP have been published so far[1-5], few researches on the deterioration of SMC in the specific environment have been conducted. It is considered that SMC containing many calcium carbonate particles as well as glass fiber is severely corroded in a corrosive solution.

This study examines the corrosion of SMC in a sodium hydroxide solution. The degradation of the mechanical characteristics was evaluated in terms of the fracture toughness value (J value). The fracture phenomenon was determined by measuring the fracture sound by the AE method as well as by observing the surface cracks and fractured surface of the test specimen. It also elucidates in detail the microscopic fracture mechanism of the deterioration of strength of SMC in the alkaline environment based on the

experimental results.

2. TEST SPECIMEN AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Used SMC was made by Polymer-mat X-664. The mechanical properties of the test specimen are shown in Table 1. The test specimen contains short fiber E-glass; 25.4mm and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) in equal quantities to each other.

The test was made using a compact tension type test specimen with a notch as illustrated in Figure 1. The notch in the test specimen so much facilitates the permeation of the solution, so that corrosion is accelerated. The other cut and drilled areas than the notch were coated with wax to prevent them from corroding by the chemicals. The test specimens used for the experiment include the untreated one kept at a room temperature of $20 \pm 4^\circ\text{C}$ and the treated one immersed in an 0.5-N sodium hydroxide solution for 10 - 30 days.

The treated test specimen was taken out from the treating solution and washed with tap water. The water remaining on the surface of it was wiped off. The test was made one hour later at the rate of elongation of 1 mm/min. An Instron-type tensile tester was used for the test and the crack opening displacement was measured with a clip-gage type displacement meter. The total AE event count and the AE event count rate (AE event counts per an unit time) were measured with an acoustic emission instrument of AE-900 series (NF Co.), and a DM-100 data recorder for recording the fracture sound. The fracture phenomenon was observed with a metallographic microscope.

3. DETERIORATION OF STRENGTH OF SMC IN SODIUM HYDROXIDE

The load-crack opening displacement curves vary according to the immersion time as shown in figure 2. The figure shows that the variation decreases from the maximum in the curve of a virgin material with the increase of the immersion time, and that the knee point (KP) apart from the linear deformation, the maximum load and the displacement at the maximum loading decrease also with it. Since those curves are similar to a load - deformation curve of an elastic-plastic material, the deterioration of the mechanical characteristics was evaluated in terms of the fracture toughness value. The $J(\text{Pmax})$ value till reaching the maximum loading calculated by the simplified Rice's theory was used as the fracture toughness value.

Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between $J(\text{Pmax})$ and the immersion time. The figure reveals that the fracture toughness value after each immersion time decreases with the increase of the immersion time and the strength is deteriorated by corrosion, though the data fluctuates to some degree as in the general mechanical properties of SMC. Next we try to make clear the cause of the deterioration of fracture toughness value using the AE method.

4. DEPENDENCE OF AE EVENT COUNTS ON IMMERSION TIME

Figure 4 (a) to (d) illustrate the variations of the AE event rates till reaching the maximum loads obtained by immersing the test specimens in an alkaline solution for different times. The positions at the knee point are shown in the figure. This reveals that the values of them decrease with the increase of the immersion time from 0 to 30 days as in Figure 2. Those figures reveal that the AE event rate begins occurring with the low crack opening displacement and sharply increase in the vicinity of the knee

point. At the knee point, AE rate makes a peak and after then, begin to increase again to achieve the maximum load. This facts shows that microscopic fracture phenomena have occurred before the begin of the mechanical property change. And it is confirmed that there are two fracture steps at the knee point and the maximum load. Furthermore, Figure 5 illustrates the variation of the total AE counts according to the immersion time. In the acid condition, the total AE counts are constant by increasing the immersion time, but in an alkaline solution as shown in Figure 5, it slightly increases than one of virgin material. Viewed from those figures revealing that the AE signal increases with the decrease of the cracks coming to the surface of the test specimen, it is confirmed that fine internal fractures and any other source exist inside the test specimen. Then, the fractured surface of the test specimen was observed to explore the surface and internal fracture of the test specimen.

5. FRACTURE MECHANISMS ON THE SPECIMEN SURFACE AT THE NOTCH TIP

It has already been published that the fracture toughness of SMC depends upon the quantity of the cracks in vicinity of the notch tip and the damaged area with micro-cracking and that the crack density is strongly affected by the environment including an acid atmosphere[6-7]. The quantity of cracks is generally respected by the crack density which is calculated from the total length of cracks per unit cracked area of the surface of test specimen and the finely cracked region at the tip is represented by the diameter of cracked area. Those parameters were, therefore, employed in this study.

The relationship between the immersion time and the crack density is shown in Figure 6. The figure reveals that the surface crack density decrease of immersion time. It seems, therefore, as if the alkaline solution inhibits the cracking. Figure 7 reveals that the diameter of damaged zone with cracking hardly changes with the increase of the immersion time. This is in a contrast to the fact that the diameter of damage zone decreases in an acid atmosphere. Although the strength is lowered with the increase of the immersion time, any fracture lowering the strength is not observed. Any internal fracture may occurs. It was examined by the AE method whether the internal fracture occurs or not.

6. DETERIORATION MECHANISMS OF SMC

It is considered that the deterioration of FRP is caused by the deteriorations of both resin and fiber and that of the interface between them. Since neither crazing nor swelling of unsaturated polyester itself was observed even by immersing in the alkaline solution, it was not considered that the resin caused the deterioration. Figure 8 shows that several fibers pulled out from the fractured surface in the vicinity of the tip of notch. Although the length of it was compared with that of a fiber pulled out from an untreated test specimen, there was no difference between them. It is, therefore, inferred from this that the deterioration of SMC is caused by the deterioration of the interface between the fiber and the resin. In fact, the surface of the fibers pulled out from the fractured surface is very smooth and pieces of the resin adhering to the fibers defined as an indication of the adhesivity were hardly observed. It is, therefore, estimated that the resin has become to be easily debonding off from the fiber.

A piece of SMC prepared by buffing the cut surface to make it smooth was immersed in a sodium solution for 30 days to investigate the effect of the sodium hydroxide on the interface between the resin and the glass fiber.

After taking out the test piece from the solution, dye was applied to the smoothen surface. A few minutes later, the dye was washed off to observe the surface. Since it was found that traces on the dye remained on the interface between the resin and the fiber, it was confirmed that voids were made by peeling off of the fiber from the resin. No longitudinal cracks were, however, observed on the glass fiber unlike that treated in hydrochloric acid.

The relationship between the peeling off and the fracture toughness value was confirmed as follows: the load was hardly transferred from the resin to the fiber due to the debonding of the interface between them; the effect preventing the notch from opening caused by bonding the interfaces with each other was lowered; the resin cracking caused by the debonding as observed in a virgin test specimen decreased, thereby reducing the surface cracking; and accordingly, fracture-absorbing energy was decreased. It was concluded that since the fiber is easily pulled out due to the debonding, the frictional sound caused by pulling out the fiber increases the fracture sound counts. From this fact, We guess that the AE sounds obtained around the knee point depend on the debonding phenomenon and over the knee point displacement, depend upon not only debonding phenomenon but also the friction sound.

7. CONCLUSION

The degradation behavior of SMC was investigated using an alkaline solution. The deterioration was researched in terms the fracture toughness value and the fracture phenomenon was studied by the observation of the surface of test specimen and by the AE method. The following results were obtained:

- 1) Although the chemical deterioration phenomena including discoloration are not observed, the fracture toughness value decreases with the increase of the immersion time, thereby causing corrosion. Corrosion increase the total AE count at the maximum load and AE event rate at the knee point.
- 2) Although the crack density on the surface of test specimen decrease with the increase of the immersion time, the diameter of the cracked region at the tip of notch is as the same as those of the virgin test specimen. From those facts, it is confirmed that an alkaline solution does not affect the molded surface but corroded the internal material at the notch tip of the specimen.
- 3) The area of permeation of dye is found at the interface between resin and fibers on the specimen immersed in the 0.5-N sodium hydroxide solution for 30 days.
- 4) For used SMC in an alkali condition from the results as shown in 1), 2) and 3), it is concluded that the interface between the resin and the fiber is so much corroded by an alkaline solution and that the resin is easily peeling off from the fiber, whereupon the strength is deteriorated.

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Table 1. Mechanical Properties of used sheet molding compounds

Mechanical and physical properties	before Knee	after Knee
Modulus of elasticity	11.00 GN/m ²	3.55 GN/m ²
Ultimate tensile strength	92.1 MN/m ²	
Poisson's ratio	0.30	0.17
Density	1.78 g/cm ³	

Fig. 1. Shapes and dimensions of the compact type specimen and the detail of the tip of the artificial notch

Fig. 2. Relation between load and crack opening displacement and degradation proceeding due to immersion with NaOHaq. KP: Knee Point. KP:Knee Point

Fig. 3. Fracture toughness value $J(P_{max})$ calculated with Rice's theory with immersion time.

Fig. 4. Variations of AE event count rate and tensile test time. KP:Knee Point, (a): virgin specimen, (b):10 days, (c):20 days, (d):30, days.

Fig. 5. Relation between the total Acoustic Emission counts and the immersion time. *1:Ref.[7]

Fig. 6. Crack density at the vicinity of notch tip dependence on immersion time.

Fig. 7. The immersion time dependence of damaged area circle at the notch tip and at the maximum load. *2:Ref.[7]

Fig. 8. Photograph of pull-out glass fibers.

Fig. 9. Photograph of glass fibers in SMC materials after immersion treatment with a solution of 0.5N NaOH. Mark: Permeation of dye.